

Versioned Archive and Review of Biotic
Interactions and Taxon Names Found within
globalbioticinteractions/yale-peabody
hash://md5/049e3fe939a2416e241ff506bc713871

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2026-06-03

Abstract

Life on Earth is sustained by complex interactions between organisms and their environment. These biotic interactions can be captured in datasets and published digitally. We present a review and archiving process for such an openly accessible digital interactions dataset of known origin and discuss its outcome. The dataset under review, named globalbioticinteractions/yale-peabody, has fingerprint hash://md5/049e3fe939a2416e241ff506bc713871, is 478MiB in size and contains 119,420 interactions with 11 unique types of associations (e.g., interactsWith) between 6,817 primary taxa (e.g., undet. Foraminifera) and 79,094 associated taxa (e.g., rocks). This report includes detailed summaries of interaction data, a taxonomic review from multiple catalogs, and an archived version of the dataset from which the reviews are derived.

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Introduction

Data Review and Archive

Data review and archiving can be a time-consuming process, especially when done manually. This review report aims to help facilitate both activities. It automates the archiving of datasets, including Darwin Core archives, and is a citable backup of a version of the dataset. Additionally, an automatic review of species interaction claims made in the dataset is generated and registered with Global Biotic Interactions (J. H. Poelen, Simons, and Mungall 2014).

This review includes summary statistics about, and observations about, the dataset under review :

Botany Division, Yale Peabody Museum - Version 396.3634
<http://ipt.peabody.yale.edu/archive.do?r=ypm-bot> 2026-06-02T23:10:53.205Z Entomology Division, Yale Peabody Museum - Version 395.3540 <http://ipt.peabody.yale.edu/archive.do?r=ypm-ent> 2026-06-02T23:10:53.205Z Invertebrate Paleontology Division, Yale Peabody Museum - Version 395.3572 <http://ipt.peabody.yale.edu/archive.do?r=ypm-ip> 2026-06-02T23:10:53.205Z Invertebrate Zoology Division, Yale Peabody Museum - Version 395.3639 <http://ipt.peabody.yale.edu/archive.do?r=ypm-iz> 2026-06-02T23:10:53.205Z Paleobotany Division, Yale Peabody Museum - Version 395.3616 <http://ipt.peabody.yale.edu/archive.do?r=ypm-pb> 2026-06-02T23:10:53.205Z Vertebrate Paleontology Division, Yale Peabody Museum - Version 395.3637 <http://ipt.peabody.yale.edu/archive.do?r=ypm-vp> 2026-06-02T23:10:53.205Z Vertebrate Zoology Division - Herpetology, Yale Peabody Museum - Version 395.3600 <http://ipt.peabody.yale.edu/archive.do?r=ypm-vz-her> 2026-06-02T23:10:53.205Z Vertebrate Zoology Division - Ichthyology, Yale Peabody Museum - Version 395.3554 <http://ipt.peabody.yale.edu/archive.do?r=ypm-vz-ich> 2026-06-02T23:10:53.205Z Vertebrate Zoology Division

- Mammalogy, Yale Peabody Museum - Version 397.3611
http://ipt.peabody.yale.edu/archive.do?r=yym-vz-mam 2026-06-02T23:10:53.205Z Vertebrate Zoology Division - Ornithology, Yale Peabody Museum - Version 395.3585 http://ipt.peabody.yale.edu/archive.do?r=yym-vz-orn 2026-06-02T23:10:53.205Z hash://md5/049e3fe939a2416e241ff506bc713871

Methods

The review is performed through programmatic scripts that leverage tools like Preston (Elliott et al. 2025), Elton (Kuhn, Poelen, and Leinweber 2025), Nomer (Salim and Poelen 2025), globinizer (J. Poelen, Seltmann, and Mietchen 2024) combined with third-party tools like grep, mlr, tail and head.

Table 1: Tools used in this review process

tool name	version
preston	0.11.1
elton	0.16.11
nomer	0.6.5
globinizer	0.4.0
mlr	6.0.0
jq	1.6
yq	4.25.3
pandoc	3.1.6.1
duckdb	1.3.1
mapserver	7.6.4

The review process can be described in the form of the script below ¹.

```
# get versioned copy of the dataset (size approx. 478MiB) under review
elton pull globalbioticinteractions/yale-peabody

# generate review notes
elton review globalbioticinteractions/yale-peabody \
  > review.tsv

# export indexed interaction records
elton interactions globalbioticinteractions/yale-peabody \
  > interactions.tsv
```

¹Note that you have to first get the data (e.g., via `elton pull globalbioticinteractions/yale-peabody`) before being able to generate reviews (e.g., `elton review globalbioticinteractions/yale-peabody`), extract interaction claims (e.g., `elton interactions globalbioticinteractions/yale-peabody`), or list taxonomic names (e.g., `elton names globalbioticinteractions/yale-peabody`)

```
# export names and align them with the Catalogue of Life using Nomer
elton names globalbioticinteractions/yale-peabody \
| nomer append col \
> name-alignment.tsv
```

or visually, in a process diagram.

Figure 1: Review Process Overview

You can find a copy of the full review script at `check-data.sh`. See also GitHub and Codeberg.

Results

In the following sections, the results of the review are summarized ². Then, links to the detailed review reports are provided.

Files

An extensive list of files produced as part of the review process can be found in Appendix A. Review Files.

Archived Dataset

Note that `data.zip` file in this archive contains the complete, unmodified archived dataset under review.

Biotic Interactions

In this review, biotic interactions (or biotic associations) are modeled as a primary (aka subject, source) organism interacting with an associate (aka object, target) organism. The dataset under review classified the primary/associate organisms with specific taxa. The primary and associate organisms The kind of interaction is documented as an interaction type.

The dataset under review, named `globalbioticinteractions/yale-peabody`, has fingerprint hash: `//md5/049e3fe939a2416e241ff506bc713871`, is 478MiB in size and

²Disclaimer: The results in this review should be considered friendly, yet naive, notes from an unsophisticated robot. Please keep that in mind when considering the review results.

Figure 2: Biotic Interaction Data Model

contains 119,420 interactions with 11 unique types of associations (e.g., interactsWith) between 6,817 primary taxa (e.g., undet. Foraminifera) and 79,094 associated taxa (e.g., rocks).

An exhaustive list of indexed interaction claims can be found in gzipped csv, tsv, geopackage and parquet archives. To facilitate discovery, a preview of claims available in the gzipped html page at indexed-interactions.html.gz are shown below.

The exhaustive list was used to create the following data summaries below.

Table 2: Sample of Indexed Interaction Claims

sourceTaxonName	interactionTypeName	targetTaxonName	referenceCitation
Aegithalos caudatus macedonicus	interactsWith	ORN.113916	http://collections.peabody.yale.edu/search/Record/ORN-065637
Erithacus rubecula rubecula	interactsWith	ORN.140511.001	http://collections.peabody.yale.edu/search/Record/ORN-140507.001
Molothrus ater ater	hasHost	ORN.142308	http://collections.peabody.yale.edu/search/Record/ORN-142309
Doricha enicura	interactsWith	ORN.142510.001	http://collections.peabody.yale.edu/search/Record/ORN-142516

Table 3: Most Frequently Mentioned Interaction Types (up to 20 most frequent)

interactionTypeName	count
interactsWith	55775
coOccursWith	46625
adjacentTo	14556
hasHost	1893

interactionTypeName	count
hasParasite	386
visitsFlowersOf	106
symbiontOf	50
preysOn	13
preyedUponBy	7
visits	6
eats	3

Table 4: Most Frequently Mentioned Primary Taxa (up to 20 most frequent)

sourceTaxonName	count
undet. Foraminifera	20312
undet. Rugoglobigerinidae	5817
undet. Rotaliida	3810
Verneuilinoides kansasensis	2065
taxon undetermined	1970
undet. Globigerinina	1464
undet. Bivalvia	1357
Limopsis striatopunctatus	1253
undet. Heterohelicidae	1167
undet. Echinoidea	1095
Atrypa reticularis	1064
Cibicidoides eocaenus	1039
Protocardia sp.	1039
Diptera	1007
Verneuilina canadensis	963
Scaphites sp.	896
Composita sp.	789
Rotaliida	736
undet. Mollusca	697

Table 5: Most Frequently Mentioned Associate Taxa (up to 20 most frequent)

targetTaxonName	count
rocks	1439
IP.856874	704
IP.856866	654
trees	649

targetTaxonName	count
IP.856867	635
IP.856873	631
IP.856871	612
IP.856872	553
IP.856903	514
IP.856879	509
IP.856868	468
IP.856404	448
IP.856906	427
IP.238722	427
IP.856876	401
IP.856902	365
IP.856388	362
earth	351
a tree	339

Table 6: Most Frequent Interactions between Primary and Associate Taxa (up to 20 most frequent)

sourceTaxonName	interactionTypeName	targetTaxonName	count
undet. Foraminifera	coOccursWith	IP.856866	653
undet. Foraminifera	coOccursWith	IP.856867	634
undet. Foraminifera	coOccursWith	IP.856871	611
undet. Foraminifera	coOccursWith	IP.856868	467
undet. Foraminifera	interactsWith	IP.856879	411
undet. Foraminifera	coOccursWith	IP.238722	389
undet. Foraminifera	coOccursWith	IP.856388	339
undet. Foraminifera	coOccursWith	IP.238721	297
undet. Foraminifera	coOccursWith	IP.856874	281
undet. Rotaliida	coOccursWith	IP.856874	280
undet. Rotaliida	coOccursWith	IP.856872	271
undet. Foraminifera	coOccursWith	IP.856873	253
undet. Foraminifera	coOccursWith	IP.856865	239
Rotaliida	coOccursWith	IP.856905	230
undet. Rotaliida	coOccursWith	IP.856873	229
undet. Foraminifera	coOccursWith	IP.856876	221
Rotaliida	coOccursWith	IP.856903	215
undet. Foraminifera	coOccursWith	IP.856875	213
undet. Foraminifera	coOccursWith	IP.856404	211

Interaction Networks

The figures below provide a graph view on the dataset under review. The first shows a summary network on the kingdom level, and the second shows how interactions on the family level. It is important to note that both network graphs were first aligned taxonomically using the Catalogue of Life. Please refer to the original (or verbatim) taxonomic names for a more original view on the interaction data.

Figure 3: Interactions on taxonomic kingdom rank as interpreted by the Catalogue of Life download [svg](#)

You can download the indexed dataset under review at indexed-interactions.csv.gz. A tab-separated file can be found at indexed-interactions.tsv.gz

Geospatial Distribution

If geospatial information was extracted from the dataset under review, the map below will show their distribution. These maps were generated using MapServer (McKenna et al. 2025) tools configured via map configuration [indexed-interactions.map](#) :

```
MAP
  SIZE 1600 800
  EXTENT -180 -90 180 90
  PROJECTION
    "init=epsg:4326"
  END
  LAYER # MODIS WMS map from NASA
    NAME      "modis_nasa"
    TYPE      RASTER
    OFFSITE   0 0 0
```


Figure 4: Interactions on the taxonomic family rank as interpreted by the Catalogue of Life. [download svg](#)

```

STATUS      ON
CONNECTIONTYPE WMS
CONNECTION "https://gibs.earthdata.nasa.gov/wms/epsg4326/best/wms.cgi?"

METADATA
  "wms_srs" "EPSG:4326"
  "wms_name" "OSM_Land_Water_Map"
  "wms_server_version" "1.1.1"
  "wms_format" "image/jpeg"
END
CLASS
  STYLE
    COLOR      232 232 232
    OUTLINECOLOR 32 32 32
  END
END
LAYER
  NAME "indexed-interactions"
  TYPE POLYGON
  STATUS ON
  CONNECTIONTYPE OGR
  CONNECTION "indexed-interactions-h3.gpkg"
  DATA "indexed-interactions-h3"
  CLASS
    STYLE
      COLORRANGE 253.0 231.0 37.0 32.0 164.0 134.0
      DATARANGE 0.3010299956639812 4.40440605092127
      RANGEITEM "log_number_of_records"
      OUTLINECOLOR 0 0 0
    END
  END
END
END

```

Associated data can be found in the geopackage files at indexed-interactions.gpkg for point data and indexed-interactions-h3.gpkg for data clustered in geospatial h3 hexagonals.

Learn more about the structure of this download at GloBI website, by opening a GitHub issue, or by sending an email.

Another way to discover the dataset under review is by searching for it on the GloBI website.

Figure 5: Hexagonal grid cells indicate that interactions claims are available for selected geospatial area: light yellow means relatively fewer claims, dark green relatively more claims.

Taxonomic Alignment

As part of the review, all names are aligned against various name catalogs (e.g., col, ncbi, discoverlife, gbif, itis, wfo, mdd, tpt, pbdb, and worms). These alignments can help review name usage or aid in selecting of a suitable taxonomic name resource.

Table 7: Sample of Name Alignments

providedName	relationName	resolvedCatalogName	resolvedName
Clay over sandstone rock at entrance triangular fault damp	NONE	col	Clay over sandstone rock at entrance triangular fault damp
Balsamea	SYNONYM_OF	col	Commiphora
Bank along an old road	NONE	col	Bank along an old road
Bank	NONE	col	Bank

Table 8: Distribution of Taxonomic Ranks of Aligned Names by Catalog. Names that were not aligned with a catalog are counted as NAs. So, the total number of unaligned names for a catalog will be listed in their NA row.

resolvedCatalogName	resolvedRank	count
col	NA	5211
col	class	37
col	family	191
col	genus	982
col	gigaclass	1
col	infraclass	1
col	infraorder	6
col	kingdom	3
col	order	57
col	parvphylum	1
col	phylum	13
col	species	3716
col	subclass	6
col	subfamily	13
col	subgenus	16
col	suborder	12
col	subphylum	5
col	subspecies	192
col	subtribe	2
col	superfamily	23
col	superorder	2
col	tribe	11
col	variety	25
discoverlife	NA	10426
discoverlife	species	15
gbif	NA	4606
gbif	class	32
gbif	family	195
gbif	form	9
gbif	genus	1007
gbif	kingdom	4
gbif	order	45
gbif	phylum	12
gbif	species	4310
gbif	subspecies	216
gbif	variety	75
itis	NA	7277
itis	class	32
itis	family	126

resolvedCatalogName	resolvedRank	count
itis	genus	393
itis	infraorder	4
itis	kingdom	3
itis	order	50
itis	phylum	11
itis	section	1
itis	species	2286
itis	subclass	12
itis	subfamily	7
itis	suborder	17
itis	subphylum	6
itis	subspecies	175
itis	superclass	2
itis	superfamily	13
itis	superorder	2
itis	variety	34
mdd	NA	10440
ncbi	NA	7686
ncbi	clade	10
ncbi	class	31
ncbi	cohort	1
ncbi	family	121
ncbi	genus	419
ncbi	infraclass	1
ncbi	infraorder	5
ncbi	kingdom	2
ncbi	order	48
ncbi	phylum	11
ncbi	species	1989
ncbi	subclass	11
ncbi	subfamily	7
ncbi	subgenus	6
ncbi	suborder	10
ncbi	subphylum	3
ncbi	subspecies	69
ncbi	superclass	2
ncbi	superfamily	15
ncbi	superorder	2
ncbi	tribe	1
ncbi	varietas	1
pdb	NA	8146
pdb	class	45
pdb	family	184
pdb	genus	791

resolvedCatalogName	resolvedRank	count
pbdb	informal	1
pbdb	infraclass	2
pbdb	infraorder	4
pbdb	kingdom	5
pbdb	order	88
pbdb	phylum	15
pbdb	species	1079
pbdb	subclass	12
pbdb	subfamily	14
pbdb	suborder	28
pbdb	subphylum	3
pbdb	subspecies	13
pbdb	superclass	3
pbdb	superfamily	28
pbdb	superorder	4
pbdb	superphylum	1
pbdb	tribe	2
pbdb	unranked clade	21
tpt	NA	10257
tpt	family	6
tpt	genus	13
tpt	order	4
tpt	species	160
wfo	NA	8566
wfo	class	1
wfo	family	4
wfo	genus	151
wfo	order	1
wfo	phylum	1
wfo	section	1
wfo	species	1685
wfo	subspecies	19
wfo	variety	18
worms	NA	8562
worms	class	38
worms	family	137
worms	genus	543
worms	gigaclass	1
worms	infraclass	1
worms	infraorder	5
worms	kingdom	3
worms	order	54
worms	parvphylum	1
worms	phylum	13

resolvedCatalogName	resolvedRank	count
worms	species	1020
worms	subclass	11
worms	subfamily	2
worms	suborder	19
worms	subphylum	5
worms	subspecies	13
worms	superclass	2
worms	superfamily	16
worms	superorder	1
worms	variety	1

Table 9: Name relationship types per catalog. Name relationship type “NONE” means that a name was not recognized by the associated catalog. “SAME_AS” indicates either a “HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME” or “SYNONYM_OF” name relationship type. We recognize that “SYNONYM_OF” encompasses many types of nomenclatural synonymies (ICZN 1999) (e.g., junior synonym, senior synonyms).

resolvedCatalogName	relationName	count
col	NONE	80190
col	SYNONYM_OF	2857
col	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	4419
discoverlife	NONE	85962
discoverlife	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	14
discoverlife	SYNONYM_OF	2
gbif	NONE	79407
gbif	SYNONYM_OF	2979
gbif	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	5499
itis	NONE	82518
itis	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	2746
itis	SYNONYM_OF	784
mdd	NONE	85853
mdd	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	104
mdd	SYNONYM_OF	1
ncbi	NONE	82858
ncbi	SAME_AS	2786
ncbi	SYNONYM_OF	356
pbdb	NONE	83215
pbdb	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	2585
pbdb	SYNONYM_OF	395
tpt	NONE	85771

resolvedCatalogName	relationName	count
tpt	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	184
tpt	SYNONYM_OF	4
wfo	NONE	83885
wfo	SYNONYM_OF	467
wfo	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	1358
wfo	HAS_UNCHECKED_NAME	375
worms	NONE	83777
worms	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	1980
worms	SYNONYM_OF	360

Table 10: List of Available Name Alignment Reports

catalog name	alignment results
col	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
ncbi	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
discoverlife	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
gbif	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
itis	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
wfo	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
mdd	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
tpt	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
pbdb	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
worms	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)

Additional Reviews

Elton, Nomer, and other tools may have difficulties interpreting existing species interaction datasets. Or, they may misbehave, or otherwise show unexpected behavior. As part of the review process, detailed review notes are kept that document possibly misbehaving, or confused, review bots. An sample of review notes associated with this review can be found below.

Table 11: First few lines in the review notes.

reviewDate	reviewCommentType	reviewComment
2026-06-03T06:15:13Z	summary	https://github.com/globalbioticinteractions/yale-peabody/archive/4525d8b90998b1d3ec3c83a5074839fce
2026-06-03T06:15:13Z	summary	119420 interaction(s)
2026-06-03T06:15:13Z	summary	0 note(s)
2026-06-03T06:15:13Z	summary	20 info(s)

In addition, you can find the most frequently occurring notes in the table below.

: Most frequently occurring review notes, if any.

For additional information on review notes, please have a look at the first 500 Review Notes in html format or the download full gzipped csv or tsv archives.

GloBI Review Badge

As part of the review, a review badge is generated. This review badge can be included in webpages to indicate the review status of the dataset under review.

Figure 6: Picture of a GloBI Review Badge ³

Note that if the badge is green, no review notes were generated. If the badge is yellow, the review bots may need some help with interpreting the species interaction data.

GloBI Index Badge

If the dataset under review has been registered with GloBI, and has been successfully indexed by GloBI, the GloBI Index Status Badge will turn green. This means that the dataset under review was indexed by GloBI and is available through GloBI services and derived data products.

Figure 7: Picture of a GloBI Index Badge ⁴

If you'd like to keep track of reviews or index status of the dataset under review, please visit GloBI's dataset index ⁵ for badge examples.

³Up-to-date status of the GloBI Review Badge can be retrieved from the GloBI Review Depot

⁴Up-to-date status of the GloBI Index Badge can be retrieved from GloBI's API

⁵At time of writing (2026-06-03) the version of the GloBI dataset index was available at

Discussion

This review and archive provides a means of creating citable versions of datasets that change frequently. This may be useful for dataset managers, including natural history collection data managers, as a backup archive of a shared Darwin Core archive. It also serves as a means of creating a trackable citation for the dataset in an automated way, while also including some information about the contents of the dataset.

This review aims to provide a perspective on the dataset to aid in understanding of species interaction claims discovered. However, it is important to note that this review does *not* assess the quality of the dataset. Instead, it serves as an indication of the open-ness⁶ and FAIRness (Wilkinson et al. 2016; Trekels et al. 2023) of the dataset: to perform this review, the data was likely openly available, **F**indable, **A**ccessible, **I**nteroperable and **R**eusable. The current Open-FAIR assessment is qualitative, and a more quantitative approach can be implemented with specified measurement units.

This report also showcases the reuse of machine-actionable (meta)data, something highly recommended by the FAIR Data Principles (Wilkinson et al. 2016). Making (meta)data machine-actionable enables more precise processing by computers, enabling even naive review bots like Nomer and Elton to interpret the data effectively. This capability is crucial for not just automating the generation of reports, but also for facilitating seamless data exchanges, promoting interoperability.

Acknowledgements

We thank the many humans that created us and those who created and maintained the data, software and other intellectual resources that were used for producing this review. In addition, we are grateful for the natural resources providing the basis for these human and bot activities. Also, thanks to <https://github.com/zygoballus> for helping improve the layout of the review tables.

Author contributions

Nomer was responsible for name alignments. Elton carried out dataset extraction, and generated the review notes. Preston tracked, versioned, and packaged, the dataset under review.

<https://globalbioticinteractions.org/datasets>

⁶According to <http://opendefinition.org/>: “Open data is data that can be freely used, reused and redistributed by anyone - subject only, at most, to the requirement to attribute and sharealike.”

Appendix A. Review Files

The following files are produced in this review:

filename	description
biblio.bib	list of bibliographic reference of this review
check-dataset.sh	data review workflow/process as expressed in a bash script
data.zip	a versioned archive of the data under review
HEAD	the digital signature of the data under review
index.docx	review in MS Word format
index.html	review in HTML format
index.md	review in Pandoc markdown format
index.pdf	review in PDF format
indexed-citations.csv.gz	list of distinct reference citations for reviewed species interaction claims in gzipped comma-separated values file format
indexed-citations.html.gz	list of distinct reference citations for reviewed species interactions claims in gzipped html file format
indexed-citations.tsv.gz	list of distinct reference citations for reviewed species interaction claims in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-interactions-col-family-col-family.svg	network diagram showing the taxon family to taxon family interaction claims in the dataset under review as interpreted by the Catalogue of Life via Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024)
indexed-interactions-col-kingdom-col-kingdom.svg	network diagram showing the taxon kingdom to taxon kingdom interaction claims in the dataset under review as interpreted by the Catalogue of Life via Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024)
indexed-interactions.csv.gz	species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in gzipped comma-separated values format

filename	description
indexed-interactions.html.gz	species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in gzipped html format
indexed-interactions.tsv.gz	species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-interactions.parquet	species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in Apache Parquet format
indexed-interactions.png	species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review plotted on a map
indexed-interactions.map	mapserver configuration to plot species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review on a map
indexed-interactions.gpkg	species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in GeoPackage format
indexed-interactions-h3.gpkg	geospatially clustered h3 species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in GeoPackage format
indexed-interactions-sample.csv	list of species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-interactions-sample.html	first 500 species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in html format
indexed-interactions-sample.tsv	first 500 species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in tab-separated values format
indexed-names.csv.gz	taxonomic names indexed from the dataset under review in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review in gzipped html format
indexed-names.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review in Apache Parquet format

filename	description
indexed-names-resolved-col.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Catalogue of Life as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-col.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Catalogue of Life as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-col.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Catalogue of Life as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-col.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Catalogue of Life as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-discoverlife.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Discover Life bee species checklist as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-discoverlife.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Discover Life bee species checklist as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format

filename	description
indexed-names-resolved-discoverlife.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Discover Life bee species checklist as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-discoverlife.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Discover Life bee species checklist as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-gbif.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with GBIF Backbone Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-gbif.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with GBIF Backbone Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-gbif.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with GBIF Backbone Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-gbif.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with GBIF Backbone Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format

filename	description
indexed-names-resolved-itis.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Integrated Taxonomic Information System (ITIS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-itis.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Integrated Taxonomic Information System (ITIS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-itis.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Integrated Taxonomic Information System (ITIS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-itis.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Integrated Taxonomic Information System (ITIS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-mdd.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Mammal Diversity Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-mdd.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Mammal Diversity Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format

filename	description
indexed-names-resolved-mdd.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Mammal Diversity Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-mdd.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Mammal Diversity Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-ncbi.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the NCBI Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-ncbi.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the NCBI Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-ncbi.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the NCBI Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-ncbi.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the NCBI Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format

filename	description
indexed-names-resolved-pbdb.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Paleobiology Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-pbdb.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Paleobiology Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-pbdb.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Paleobiology Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-pbdb.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Paleobiology Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-tpt.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Terrestrial Parasite Tracker (TPT) Taxonomic Resource as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-tpt.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Terrestrial Parasite Tracker (TPT) Taxonomic Resource as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format

filename	description
indexed-names-resolved-tpt.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Terrestrial Parasite Tracker (TPT) Taxonomic Resource as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-tpt.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Terrestrial Parasite Tracker (TPT) Taxonomic Resource as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-wfo.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World of Flora Online as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-wfo.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World of Flora Online as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-wfo.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World of Flora Online as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-wfo.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World of Flora Online as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format

filename	description
indexed-names-resolved-worms.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World Register of Marine Species (WoRMS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-worms.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World Register of Marine Species (WoRMS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-worms.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World Register of Marine Species (WoRMS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-worms.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World Register of Marine Species (WoRMS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-sample.csv	first 500 taxonomic names found in the dataset under review in comma-separated values format
indexed-names-sample.html	first 500 taxonomic names found in the dataset under review in html format
indexed-names-sample.tsv	first 500 taxonomic names found in the dataset under review in tab-separated values format
interaction.svg	diagram summarizing the data model used to index species interaction claims
nanopub-sample.trig	first 500 species interaction claims as expressed in the nanopub format (Kuhn and Dumontier 2014)

filename	description
nanopub.trig.gz	species interaction claims as expressed in the nanopub format (Kuhn and Dumontier 2014)
process.svg	diagram summarizing the data review processing workflow
prov.nq	origin of the dataset under review as expressed in rdf/nquads
review.csv.gz	review notes associated with the dataset under review in gzipped comma-separated values format
review.html.gz	review notes associated with the dataset under review in gzipped html format
review.tsv.gz	review notes associated with the dataset under review in gzipped tab-separated values format
review-sample.csv	first 500 review notes associated with the dataset under review in comma-separated values format
review-sample.html	first 500 review notes associated with the dataset under review in html format
review-sample.tsv	first 500 review notes associated with the dataset under review in tab-separated values format
review.svg	a review badge generated as part of the dataset review process
zenodo.json	metadata of this review expressed in Zenodo record metadata

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